

Empowerment and Self-Help Strategies for the Implementation of Development Projects in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State

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Abstract

The study examined empowerment and self-help strategies for the implementation of development projects in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State. Two research objectives and research questions guided the study while two null hypotheses were tested. The descriptive research design was adopted with a population of 289 community leaders and members of community-based organizations. The sample size of the study was 37 community leaders and 252 members of 12 community-based organizations. The entire population was manageable so the researcher adopted census study. The instrument for data collection was a 23 item self-developed questionnaire titled "Community Development Strategies for Implementation of Development Projects Questionnaire". The instrument was duly validated by experts, while the reliability of the instrument was determined through a test of internal consistency using Cronbach Alpha. Coefficients of 0.86, and 0.81 were obtained for the various clusters of the instrument which showed that the instrument is reliable. The research questions of the study were answered using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested using Z-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. From the analyses, findings amongst others revealed that empowerment strategy affects the construction of roads in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State to a high extent. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that government and other stake holders should establish and support institutions that facilitates community empowerment. This is achieved by creating community resource centers, providing training programmes and promoting opportunities for active participation in decision making processes

Keywords: Empowerment, Self-Help, Strategies, Implementation, Development Projects

INTRODUCTION

The term community development is made up of two words 'community' and 'development'. These words belong to the group of words regarded by philosophers as systematically ambiguous. According to Adekola and Oyebamiji (2011) "a word is systematically ambiguous when it is elastic in usage or is capable of multiple meanings and when it persists in its ambiguity in whatever context and situation it is found". This ambiguity affords scholars wide latitude to define them from different perspectives in tangent with their domain. Barikor (2009) supports this view when he acknowledged that development is a polymorphous product. In other words, it assumes a lot of forms, character and styles.

Community development therefore is ultimately about getting community members working together. Imhabekhai (2009) say community development "supports people to take collective action to tackle problems that many individuals may be experiencing or to help achieve a shared dream that many be experiencing or to help achieve a shared dream that many individuals will benefit from". The UNO (2006) in Oyebamiji and Adekola (2008) defined community development as: a process by which the efforts of the people themselves are united with those of governmental authorities, to improve the economic, social and cultural conditions of community, to integrate those communities into the life of the nation and to enable them contribute fully to national progress. This definition is practicalized in various communities in both Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre local government areas of Rivers State. Ezimah (2004) explained that education is that learning in question which contributes to the development of knowledge and understanding, in both breadth and depth. Education therefore becomes a veritable strategy in development of projects. It influences both the quality of skills developed and the level of knowledge acquired by the individual to be able to participate meaningfully in the process of development.

Community development is a far-reaching discipline which has transcended the purview of bettering the physical, social and economic conditions of the people. It even accommodates efforts geared towards improving emotional and

psychological development of the people, removing all forms of threats, inhibitions and insecurity whether internal or external that hamper people's emancipation. Indeed, community development covers far more scope than meets the eye. The scope of community development is said to be "as community life itself" (Ezimah, 2004). It is not only limited to programmes that improve the living conditions and health of the people such as agricultural extension, health, home economics, co-operatives, rural industries, housing, public amenities, recreation and leisure, but also concerned with the total development of man which covers altitudinal changes, literacy, acquisition of both occupational and social skills, increased awareness ' and self-confidence through active involvement of the people themselves in learning processes in which they learn to do by doing (Onyeozu, 2007). This agrees with Nyerere's statement that development is for man by man and of man.

Empowerment is also important for the effective implementation of any community development projects. Empowerment is a process of enabling people to act or perform. It is a process of giving local people the necessary skills, tools, resources and legal backing to perform (Oyebamiji & Adekola, 2008). Empowerment is a process of liberating individuals from the state of hopelessness. Various forms of empowerment which are: Economic Empowerment; Educational Empowerment; political Empowerment and capacity building. Economic empowerment enables the people to acquire new skills or improve on the old ones. Educational empowerment involves the introduction of new ways of doing things, literacy education and acquisition of new knowledge through formal and non-formal processes. Political empowerment comes in form of giving local people leadership skills, partaking in political decisions and understanding their countries' political structure (Eboh, Okoye & Ayichi, 2015).

According to Oyebamiji and Adekola (2008), the main thrust of self-help is the aspiration of the people themselves to achieve improvement through their own efforts to their own advantage from resources which would otherwise lay dormant. Also, self-help increases the confidence and competence of community people in the handling of their own affairs and makes them receptive to change. Oyebamiii (2008) further noted that the practice of self-help is based on:

- i. Need identification (felt-needs),
- ii. Resource mobilization: Through awareness creation and awakening of interest;
- iii. Confidence in community ability and capability to meet their needs;
- iv. Empowerment
- v. Adequate communication; and
- vi. Development of all.

Thus, Adiele (2014) noted that self-help in community development implies that a community should help itself to solve its problem by personal efforts of members of that community, and that the solution achieved by such means is more enduring and reliable, and thus more sustainable.

The aim of this study is to provide empirical information on how community development strategies like empowerment and self help can be used to assist the effective implementation of community development projects in Obio/Akpor and IkwerreLocal Government Areas of Rivers State. Also, the findings from this research will help in tackling the problem of lack of effective implementation of development projects in Ohio/Akpor and IkwerreLocal Government Areas of Rivers State.

Statement of Problem

Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas are in Rivers State, a state, rich in mineral and oil, is still struggling with community development issues. Most times, only one third or half the development plans are implemented and almost none is being sustained Problems of poverty, youth unemployment, inadequate funding, lack of mobilization or empowerment and illiteracy, and so on, of the community members are major issues affecting community development in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre local government areas of Rivers State (Anyanwu, 2002). These problems hamper effective implementation of development projects in area of the study. It is also observed that most projects carried out in the area of study are usually not the first choice of the community people, they are mostly marginalized and overlooked at the decision making process about what project is needed for implementation, also there are not enough mobilization and empowerment made before a project is carried out thereby creating a problem which distorts the implementation process of a project as the community members are mostly reluctant to partake in such projects. Also, the lack of implementation of development projects has caused many problems, especially unemployment and

poverty in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre local government areas. Hence, it is expedient to examine strategies for community development for implementing development projects in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas, Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to examine community development strategies for implementation of development projects in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State. In specific terms, the study sought to

1. examine the extent to which empowerment strategy influence the implementation of development projects in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State.
2. Ascertain the extent to which self-help strategy influence the implementation of development projects in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent does empowerment strategy influence the implementation of development projects in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State?
2. To what extent does self-help strategy influence the implementation of development projects in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses guided the study and tested at 0.05 significant levels.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of members of community members and community leaders on the extent to which empowerment strategy influence the implementation of development projects in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of members of community members and community leaders on the extent to which self-help strategy influence the implementation of development projects in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the descriptive survey design aimed at investigating Community Development Strategies for the Implementation of Development Projects in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas, Rivers State. The population for this study was 289 community leaders and members of selected 12 communities and 12 Community Based Organizations. This comprises 37 community leaders and 252 community members in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State. The sample size of this study comprised of 37 community leaders and 252 members from selected 12 communities in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State. The entire population was manageable so the researcher adopted Census sampling technique. The instrument for data collection in this study was a structured questionnaire titled “Empowerment and Self Help Strategies for Implementation of Development Projects Questionnaire” (CDSIDPQ). The instrument was divided into two sections; section A elicited information on the demographic data of the respondents, while section B comprised of 30 structured items drawn from the four research questions that guided the study. The questionnaire contains four response options to elicit the views of the respondents. The questionnaire was structured on a four-point summated rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE) = 4, High Extent (HE) = 3, Low Extent (LE) = 2, Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1.

To ensure the face and content validity of the instruments, three instruments were given to the researcher’s supervisor and two other experts, one in Adult Education and one in Measurement and Evaluation, Rivers State University. The comments and observation made by these experts were used to improve the quality of the instrument. The internal consistency of the instrument was established using the Cronbach Alpha method. By this method 20 copies of the questionnaire were administered to community leaders and members of community-based organizations in Port Harcourt Local Government Areas, which is outside the study area. Their responses were correlated using Cronbach Alpha statistics. Reliability coefficients of 0.86, and 0.81, were obtained for the various sections of the instrument respectively. The researcher administered the questionnaire to the respondents with the help of three trained research assistants who are post graduate students in the Faculty of Education, Rivers State University who aided in distributing

and retrieving the questionnaire. Instructions on how to fill the questionnaire was clearly stated to the respondents. Afterwards, all copies were retrieved and used for data analysis. The research questions were answered using Mean and Standard Deviation, while the hypotheses were tested using z-test at 0.05 level of significance. Decision rule for the research questions were based on the classification of level of extent as shown below:

RESULT

Research Question 1: To what extent does empowerment strategy influence the implementation of community development projects in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean analyses on the extent empowerment strategy influences the implementation of community development projects.

S/N	Items	Members of CBOs N=252			Community Leaders N=37		
		Mean	S.D	Decision	Mean	S.D	Remark
1	Empowerment Strategy improves the leadership skills of the community members that enables them take part in the planning process for the implementation of development projects.	2.90	0.79	HE	3.43	0.97	HE
2	Empowerment Strategy improves the literacy skills of the community members thereby helping them contribute positively to the implementation of a development project.	2.88	0.68	HE	3.41	0.96	HE
3	Empowering the community members through training programmes can enhance their knowledge and understanding about the importance of implementing a development project.	2.97	0.81	HE	3.00	0.82	HE
4	Empowering the members of the community financially to enable them start up small businesses can support the implementation of development projects.	3.14	0.86	HE	2.59	0.62	HE
5	Empowering community members with bricklaying skills will enable them contribute their skills or services in the implementation of community projects.	2.91	0.79	HE	2.73	0.75	HE
6	Through empowerment strategy, members of the community are exposed to both national and international developmental agencies that can contribute to the implementation of development projects in their community.	2.78	0.76	HE	2.76	0.78	HE
Grand Mean		2.93		HE	2.86		HE

Analyzed data in Table 1 above on research question one, revealed that the mean scores of members community based organizations (CBOs) and community leaders in item 1, are 2.90 and 3.43 means, standard deviation of 0.72 and 0.60 . Item 2 have 2.88 and 3.41 means, 0.74 and 0.68 standard deviations for members of CBOs and community leaders. Item 3 have 2.97 and 3.00 means, 0.69 and 0.69 standard deviations for members CBOs and community leaders. Item 4 have 3.14 and 2.59 means, 0.78 and 0.79 standard deviations for members CBOs and community leaders. Item 5 have 2.91 and 2.73 means, 0.78 and 0.79 standard deviations for members CBOs and community leaders. Item 6 have 2.78 and 2.76 means, 0.78 and 0.79 standard deviations for members CBOs and community leaders. This shows that both respondents agreed that, empowering community members with leadership skills will

enable them involve in the planning process of development projects, empowering community members by exposing them to both national and international development agencies to be attracted to the community for the implementing development projects in their community, community members are empowered through literacy skills for the maintenance and sustainability of development projects, members of the community are equipped with knowledge through training programmes to enhance their understanding of the goals and objectives of such projects, empowering the members of the community financially to enable them start up small businesses can support the implementation of projects and equipping community members in bricklaying skills will enable them contribute their skills and services in the implementation of community projects. With grand means of 2.93 and 2.86 for members CBOs and community leaders respectively. Therefore, the answer to research question one is that, empowerment strategy influences the implementation of community projects in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State to a high extent.

Research Question 2: To what extent does self-help strategy influence the implementation of community projects in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean analyses on the extent self-help strategy influence the implementation of community development projects.

S/N	Items	Members of CBOs N=252			Community Leaders N=37		
		Mean	S.D	Remark	Mean	S.D	Remark
7	Self-help strategy enables community members to cultivate a sense of responsibility that contributed to an effective implementation of a development project.	3.16	0.87	HE	2.95	0.81	HE
8	Through self-help strategy, the major developmental needs of the community members are identified and implemented.	2.84	0.79	HE	2.73	0.77	HE
9	Self-help strategy breeds a sense of ownership and thereby enhances citizenship participation for the implementation of development projects.	3.04	0.84	HE	2.68	0.73	HE
10	Self-help enables individuals in the community to harness their human and material resources for effective implementation of projects.	2.90	0.79	HE	3.08	0.86	HE
11	Self-help strategy enables community members to join their efforts and resources for effective implementation of development projects.	3.02	0.83	HE	3.03	0.84	HE
12	Through self-help strategy, the community people's confidence about a project is increased thereby encouraging active participation in the implementation of a development project.	2.99	0.82	HE	2.65	0.83	HE
Grand Mean		2.99		HE	2.85		HE

Analyzed data in Table 2 above on research question two, revealed that the mean scores of community-based organizations members (CBOs) and community leaders in item 7 are 3.16 and 2.95 means, standard deviations of

0.81 and 0.87. Item 8 have 2.93 and 2.80 means, 0.77 and 0.67 standard deviations for members CBOs and community leaders. Item 9 have means of 2.84 and 2.73, standard deviation of 0.67 and 0.68 for members of CBOs and community leaders. Item 10 have 2.90 and 2.68 means, 0.76 and 0.71 standard deviations for members of CBOs and community leaders. Item 11 have 3.02 and 3.03 means, 0.78 and 0.79 standard deviations for members of CBOs and community leaders. Item 12 have 2.99 and 2.65 means, 0.78 and 0.79 standard deviations for members of CBOs and community leaders. This shows that both respondents agreed that, self-help strategy enables community members to cultivate a sense of responsibility towards the sustainability of community development projects, the community development project implemented is relevant and beneficial to the needs of the community members through self-help, here is a sense of ownership among community members as they take part in problem identification and implementation of projects, self-help enables individuals in the community to harness their human and material resources for effective implementation of projects, community development projects are sustained as community members join efforts and resources in solving their human and material resources for effective implementation of projects and increases the people's confidence in the projects to be implemented thereby increasing active participation in the projects. With grand means of 2.99 and 2.85 for members of CBOs and community leaders respectively. The answer to research question two is that self-help strategy influences the implementation of development projects in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State to a high extent.

Hypotheses

H₀₁ There is no significant difference in the mean rating of community-based organizations and community leaders on the extent to which empowerment strategy influence the implementation of development projects in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State.

Table 3 Hypothesis one using Z-test Statistics

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	S.D	SL	DF	Z-cal	Z-tab.	Decision
Members of CBOs	252	2.93	0.78	0.05	287	0.50	±1.96	Sig.
Community Leaders	37	2.56	0.82					

Table 3 above shows that the z-calculated value of 0.50 is less than the z-table value of ± 1.96 for degree of freedom (287) at 0.05 significant level suggesting that there is no significant difference between the responses of members of community based organizations (CBOs) and community leaders on the extent to which empowerment strategy influence the implementation of development projects in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State. This therefore means that the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternate hypothesis, rejected.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of community-based organizations and community leaders on the extent to which self-help strategy influences the implementation of development projects in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State.

Table 4 Hypothesis two using Z-test Statistics

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	S.D	SL	DF	Z-cal	Z-tab.	Decision
Members of CBOs	252	2.99	0.82	0.05	287	1.17	±1.96	Sig
Community Leaders	37	2.85	0.66					

Table 4 above shows that the z-calculated value of 1.17 is less than the z-table value of ± 1.96 for degree of freedom (287) at 0.05 significant level suggesting that there is no significant difference between the responses of CBOs and community leaders on the extent to which self-help strategy influences the implementation of development projects

in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State. This therefore means that the null hypothesis is accepted and the alternate hypothesis, rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The result of the finding of the study for research question one revealed that empowerment strategy influences the implementation of development projects in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State to a high extent. It was revealed that, empowering community members with leadership skills enabled them involved in the planning process of development projects, empowering community members by exposing them to both national and international development agencies to be attracted to the community for implementing development projects in their community, community members are empowered through literacy skills for the maintenance and sustainability of development projects, members of the communities are equipped with knowledge through training programmes to enhance their understanding of the d them start up small businesses to support the implementation of projects and equipping community members in bricklaying skills enabled them contribute their skills and services in the implementation of community projects. The corresponding hypothesis one revealed that, there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of members of community based organizations and community leaders on the extent to which empowerment strategy influences the implementation of development projects in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State. This finding is in line with the finding of Oyebamiji and Adekola (2008) which revealed that empowerment is also important for the effective implementation of any community development projects. Empowerment is a process of enabling people to act or perform. It is a process of giving local people the necessary skills, tools, resources and legal backing to perform (2008). He also noted the various forms of empowerment which are: Economic Empowerment; Educational Empowerment; political Empowerment and capacity building.

The result of the finding of the study for research question two revealed that self-help strategy influences the implementation of development projects in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State to a high extent. It was revealed that, self-help strategy enables community members to cultivate a sense of responsibility towards the sustainability of community development projects, the community development project implemented is relevant and beneficial to the needs of the community members through self-help, there is a sense of ownership among community members as they take part in problem identification and implementation of projects, self-help enables individuals in the community to harness their human and material resources for effective implementation of projects, community development projects are sustained as community members join efforts and resources in solving their human and material resources for effective implementation of projects and increases the people's confidence in the projects to be implemented thereby increasing active participation in the projects. The corresponding hypothesis two revealed that, there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of members of community based organizations and community leaders on the extent to which self-help strategy influences the implementation of development projects in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State. This agrees with the findings of Cahill (2013) which revealed that the main thrust of self-help is the aspiration of the people themselves to achieve improvement through their own efforts to their own advantage from resources which would otherwise lay dormant. Also, self-help increases the confidence and competence of community people in the handling of their own affairs and makes them receptive to change.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that “community development strategies (empowerment strategy, and self-help strategy, for implementation of development projects are paramount in enhancing community development in Obio/Akpor and Ikwerre Local Government Areas of Rivers State. In other words, the adoption of these strategies has enhanced the effective implementation of community development project in the aforementioned study areas by promoting ownership, active involvement and sustainable outcomes leading to more effective implementation of community development projects.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, it was recommended that:

1. Both the government, stakeholders and empowerment institutions should establish and support institutions that facilitates community empowerment. These are achieved by creating community resource centers, providing training programs and promoting opportunities for active participation in decision making processes
2. Government should allocate financial resources to support community-driven initiatives through the establishment of funding mechanisms specifically designed to support self-help projects.

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